

Methods for Estimating the Health Effects of Environmental Mixtures

Mandy Yao¹, Emily Cauble², Mike Kleeman³, Sophia Wang², and Meredith Franklin¹

¹Department of Statistical Sciences, University of Toronto, 27 King's College Cir, Toronto, ON M5S 1A1

²Department of Computational and Quantitative Medicine, City of Hope, 1500 East Duarte Road, Duarte, CA 91010

³Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of California, Davis, 1 Shields Ave, Davis, CA 95616

Abstract: Wildfire events have been increasing in frequency, duration, and severity. Coupled with these events is poor air quality, which is known to be detrimental to health. Air pollution is a complex mixture, and traditional approaches to understanding exposure-health associations, which typically examine one pollutant at a time, do not capture the multidimensional dynamics and correlational structure of its multiple co-existing components. While some multi-pollutant modelling strategies have been developed, there remain shortcomings. We adapt a principal stratification approach so that its application can be generalized to a broad range of environmental and health data. We demonstrate these developments using chemically speciated particulate matter air pollution concentrations coupled with satellite-derived wildfire smoke plumes in the Western United States.

Keywords: Principal Stratification, Multi-Pollutant Models, Propensity Score Matching, Sliced Inverse Regression

1 Introduction

In recent years, wildfire events have become more frequent and destructive. Coupled with these events is poor air quality, due to smoke and winds, which has significant public health implications.

Increased health effects have been observed during wildfire events. Elderly people enrolled in the U.S. Medicare insurance system showed increased hospitalizations for respiratory disease 7.2% (95% CI: 0.25%, 15%) on days with elevated wildfire $PM_{2.5}$ levels (Peng et al. (2022)). In a study in Southern California, $PM_{2.5}$ from wildfires was shown to be more detrimental to health than $PM_{2.5}$ from other sources (Aguilera et al. (2021)). The reason for the differential toxicity between sources is linked to the fact that particulate matter is itself complex chemically, with chemical signatures that differ depending on the source. For example, wildfires in the western U.S. have been shown to produce particles with increased organic and elemental carbon (OC and EC), as well as crustal elements (silicon, Si and aluminum, Al) (Liu and Peng (2018)). In California specifically, wildfire $PM_{2.5}$ was shown to have elevated aluminum, sulfate, and in some fires, copper and lead (Boaggio et al. (2022)).

Examining the health effects associated with single pollutants (e.g. $PM_{2.5}$) does not address the true complexity of the problem. Disentangling which components have greater health impacts requires multipollutant modeling approaches, which are less straightforward than those used to examine single pollutants (Peng et al. (2022)). This is due in part to the multidimensional nature and correlational structure of multiple pollutants when they are examined simultaneously. Single-pollutant models look at effects of individual pollutants while adjusting for potential confounders

such as meteorology (Dominici et al. (2010)). This allows for easy interpretation of effect estimates, often represented as relative risks per increase in pollutant exposure. While multi-pollutant models consider correlations between multiple pollutants, the interpretation of health effects is more complicated because of the unordered high-dimensional multi-pollutant exposure space. To address this, the interpretation of health effects has focused on a few important pollutants and assumed that the other pollutants’ concentrations remained constant. However, this assumption is impossible to maintain in practice.

One approach to this problem suggested by Peng et al. (2022) enables the examination of multiple pollutants while maintaining ease of interpretation through principal stratification. It combines dimension reduction techniques and causal inference methodology to deal with high dimensional pollutant data while utilizing an external mixture-altering contrast to produce interpretable risk estimates.

As presented in Peng et al. (2022), the principal stratification method combines wildfire information with chemically speciated $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations to estimate association with health outcomes through the contrast in particle composition on wildfire and non-wildfire days. However, a limitation of this approach is that it does not consider the possibility of a time lag between exposure to air pollution and health outcome. Exposure lags have been shown to be important considerations in examining air pollution health effects (Schwartz (2000)). To address this, we incorporate a distributed lag model, which can account for relationships between exposures and outcomes at different time lags in a flexible manner (Gasparrini et al. (2010)). We use simulated data to demonstrate the use of these models.

In section 2 of this report the principal stratification method is outlined and demonstrated on a combination of observed and simulated data. In section 3, distributed lag models are presented and used to extend the principal stratification method. In section 4 limitations of these models are discussed and additional extensions are proposed.

2 Principal Stratification Method

The combined daily multi-pollutant and wildfire data used to estimate their impact on health outcomes involves a principal stratification approach developed by Peng et al (2022) Peng et al. (2022).

Principal stratification compares respiratory hospitalization rates associated with $PM_{2.5}$ components on "smoke days" and "non-smoke days". This is achieved in three steps. First, propensity score matching is used to match smoke days to non-smoke days and make a dataset containing these matched days. Second, sliced inversed regression (SIR) is used to create a projection that shows the difference in the $PM_{2.5}$ components on smoke days versus non-smoke days. Third, principal stratification is used to estimate the effect of this difference on respiratory hospitalization.

2.1 Propensity Score Matching

The R `MatchIt` package was used to perform the propensity score matching. We use it to model $Pr(Z_t = 1|w_t)$, where Z_t is an indicator for smoke day, t denotes the day and w_t is a vector of covariates that can affect the probability of a smoke day, such as temperature and humidity. Here, $Z_t = 1$ denotes a smoke day and $Z_t = 0$ denotes a non-smoke day. The probability is modelled using logistic regression and the matched dataset is created using the default nearest neighbour matching algorithm from the package.

We want to use the matched dataset so that we can find a weighting that gives greater influence to days where overall $PM_{2.5}$ levels are not predicted to change because of wildfire smoke. This is important because we need to control for the overall level of the pollutant since it is already known that higher $PM_{2.5}$ levels are associated with increased respiratory hospitalizations.

This can be done by finding days where $\Delta_t = PM_t(1) - PM_t(0) < \epsilon$ where $PM_t(1)$ is the overall level of $PM_{2.5}$ on smoke day t and $PM_t(0)$ is the overall level of $PM_{2.5}$ on non-smoke day t . The issue here is that on any given day, we only observe either a smoke day or a non-smoke day. As a result, we can instead model the outcomes for both a smoke day and non-smoke day on each day t with a bivariate Normal distribution. Then we predict the conditional mean of $PM_t(1)$ and

$PM_t(0)$ as

$$E[PM_t(1)|PM_t(0), v_t] = v_t'\xi + \tau + \omega \frac{\eta_1}{\eta_0} (PM_t(0) - v_t'\xi),$$

$$E[PM_t(0)|PM_t(1), v_t] = v_t'\xi + \omega \frac{\eta_0}{\eta_1} (PM_t(1) - v_t'\xi - \tau),$$

where v_t is a vector of baseline covariates, ω is a correlation coefficient, $\tau = E[PM_t(1) - PM_t(0)]$, ξ is a vector of regression coefficients and η_0 and η_1 are the standard deviations of $PM_t(0)$ and $PM_t(1)$ respectively.

In order to put less weight on days where overall $PM_{2.5}$ levels are predicted to change significantly because of a smoke wave, we can use the weights $u_t \sim \exp(-\frac{1}{2}(PM_t(1) - PM_t(0))^2/b)$, where for each day t , one of $PM_t(1)$ and $PM_t(0)$ is observed and the other is predicted from the model above. b defines when the difference between $PM_t(1)$ and $PM_t(0)$ is thought to be "small". We can choose a larger b to be able to include more observations or a smaller b to keep the difference between $PM_t(1)$ and $PM_t(0)$ smaller.

For the application, the aim was to create a dataset that matches smoke days to non-smoke days while keeping other characteristics of these pairs of days as similar as possible. This was accomplished by controlling for month, year, county, daily temperature, and dew point temperature in matching. It was especially important to consider the county variable in the matching to avoid confounding from spatial contrast between counties that can be far from each other because counties could have other characteristics that vary due to their locations.

2.2 Sliced Inverse Regression

To show the difference in the $PM_{2.5}$ mixture between smoke days and non-smoke days, we use a projection of the chemical speciation data called the principal mixture direction. This is produced using sliced inverse regression (SIR) for binary outcomes.

We create a standardized constituent matrix $R = \Sigma_M^{-1/2}(\tilde{M} - E[\tilde{M}])$, where $\tilde{M} = U^{1/2}M$ is a weighted chemical constituent matrix and Σ_M is the covariance matrix of \tilde{M} . Here, for n days of observations in the matched dataset and p chemical constituents of $PM_{2.5}$, M is an $n \times p$ matrix and $U = \text{diag}(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n)$ is an $n \times n$ matrix of the propensity score matching weights u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n . Then the group mean difference of the rows of R between smoke days and non-smoke days can be used to estimate a principal mixture direction

$$\gamma = \left(\frac{R'z}{z'z} - \frac{R'(1-z)}{(1-z)'(1-z)} \right) \Sigma_M^{-1/2},$$

where $z = (z_1, \dots, z_n)$ is a vector of smoke day indicators where for day t , $z_t = 1$ indicates a smoke day and $z_t = 0$ indicates a non-smoke day. γ can be used to create a principal mixture score $x_t = (m_t - \bar{m})'\gamma$ for each day t , where m_t is an observed set of chemical constituents and \bar{m} is a vector of means for each chemical constituent. This score characterizes each day's chemical constituents as being more "smoke day like" for strongly positive values and more "non-smoke day like" for strongly negative values.

2.3 Principal Stratification

Using the principal mixture scores, we perform principal stratification to estimate the effect of the composition of air components on respiratory hospitalization. we use the principal strata $x_t(1) - x_t(0)$, where $x_t(1)$ and $x_t(0)$ are the observed scores on smoke days and non-smoke days, respectively. Since we can only obtain one of these values on a given day, we treat the other value as missing data and use a bivariate Normal distribution to model both values:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_t(1) \\ x_t(0) \end{pmatrix} \sim N \left(\begin{pmatrix} h_t'\theta + \xi \\ h_t'\theta \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1^2 & \rho\sigma_1\sigma_0 \\ \rho\sigma_1\sigma_0 & \sigma_0^2 \end{pmatrix} \right). \quad (1)$$

Here, h is a vector of covariates that are factors, such as temperature and humidity, useful for predicting mixture scores, θ is a vector of coefficients and ξ is the additive effect of smoke days on the mixture score. This is used to infer the missing value given the observed value on each day.

If we let $Y_t(1)$ and $Y_t(0)$ be the rate of respiratory hospitalization of smoke and non-smoke day t , respectively, we can use a Poisson distribution to model the health outcome:

$$Y_t(z_t)|x_t(1), x_t(0) \sim \text{Poisson}(\mu_t(z_t)),$$

$$\log \mu_t(z_t) = r_t' \alpha + \delta z_t + z_t f(x_t(1) - x_t(0)),$$

where $z_t = 1$ for smoke day t , $z_t = 0$ for non smoke day t , r is a vector of baseline covariates and α is a vector of regression coefficients. We estimate a smooth function f , which could give an idea of the kind of relationship between difference in principal mixture score and risk of respiratory hospitalization.

We can then estimate

$$\log \frac{E[Y_t(1)|x_t(1), x_t(0)]}{E[Y_t(0)|x_t(1), x_t(0)]} = \delta + f(x_t(1) - x_t(0)),$$

where δ is the change in the risk of respiratory hospitalization when there is no difference in principal mixture scores. 95% confidence intervals are created for the log-relative risk estimates using the Bootstrap procedure. Resampling is done separately in the matched dataset for the smoke day and non-smoke day observations.

2.3.1 Principal Stratification Sensitivity Analyses

To test the sensitivity of the principal stratification model to specifications of the parameters ρ, ω and b , we examined the model behavior under different parameter values. We allowed $/rho$ and $/omega$, which are the parameters for the correlation between the potential $PM_{2.5}$ outcomes and the principal mixture scores, respectively, to vary between 0.2 and 0.8. The parameter b (which defines when the difference between $PM_t(1)$ and $PM_t(0)$ is thought to be "small" in the weights used for the propensity score matching) varied between 0.4 and 1.5.

3 Extension: Distributed Lag Model

Principal stratification does not capture lags in the exposure-response function. To address this limitation, we incorporated a distributed lag approach in the time dimension (Gasparrini et al. (2010)).

Distributed lag models are able to model relationships between exposure and outcomes at different time lags so that we can learn about exposure windows having stronger associations with the outcome. To understand the model specification for DLMs, we can start with a general model representation for outcomes Y_t :

$$g(\mu_t) = \alpha + \sum_{j=1}^J s_j(x_{tj}; \beta_j) + \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_k u_{tk},$$

where $\mu \equiv E(Y)$, g is a monotonic link function, and Y has a distribution from the exponential family. s_j are smooth functions that describe the relationship between x_j and the linear predictor with parameters β_j . The final sum includes linear effects from predictors u_k with coefficients γ_k in the model.

The smooth functions $s(x)$ can be represented using basis functions, which are known transformations on x that generate variables called basis variables. A $n \times v_x$ basis matrix Z is then created from applying the basis functions to the vector of exposures x . This representation for n observations is given by

$$s(x_t; \beta) = z_t^T \beta,$$

where z_t is the t th row of Z .

To incorporate lags $l = [0, \dots, l, \dots, L]^T$ with L being the maximum lag, we look at relationships between past exposures x_{t-l} and the outcome. We can create a $n \times (L + 1)$ matrix Q with

$$q_t = [x_t, \dots, x_{t-l}, \dots, x_{t-L}]^T.$$

Finally, we define a DLM in matrix notation using

$$s(x_t; \eta) = q_t^T C \eta,$$

where C is a $(L + 1) \times v_l$ matrix of basis variables and η is a vector of unknown parameters. C is obtained from applying the basis functions to the lag vector l .

3.1 Distributed Lag Non-Linear Models

Since exposure-outcome and time-outcome relationships can be complex, it may be useful to model these as non-linear relationships. Distributed lag non-linear models (DLNMs) have been used for this purpose (Gasparrini et al. (2010)). We now choose two sets of basis functions to describe both the exposure-outcome relationships and distributed lag effects. We then combine these basis functions to create cross-basis functions.

To specify a DLNM, we find a matrix Z like before but add a dimension for lag for each basis variable of x in Z to create a $n \times v_x \times (L + 1)$ array \tilde{R} . In this matrix, vectors r_{tj} are the transformed lagged exposures for time t through basis function j . With this, we can define a DLNM using

$$s(x_t; \eta) = \sum_{j=1}^{v_x} \sum_{k=1}^{v_l} r_{tj}^T \cdot c_{jk} \eta_{jk} = w_t^T \eta,$$

where w_t is obtained by transforming x_t using the $v_x \cdot v_l$ cross-basis functions.

3.2 DLM and Principal Stratification

To incorporate a DLNM into the principal stratification method, we used the `dlm` R package and create a crossbasis matrix using the data from the analysis (Gasparrini (2011)). Then the Poisson GLM model from the principal stratification method with the crossbasis and use the `crosspred` function to generate predictions. The results can be visualized using 3-D plots (with time, exposure, and outcome variables) and contour plots.

To evaluate the effect of smoke days, the DLNM included an interaction between the smoke variable and total $PM_{2.5}$ through the crossbasis matrix. Furthermore, we used natural splines with 3 degrees of freedom to allow for sufficient flexibility without overfitting. An additional sensitivity analysis was done to see if the results were affected by using different splines or different degrees of freedom.

3.3 Data

3.4 Observed Data

In Peng et al. (2022), the authors used data from the Western US from 2004 to 2009 for the analysis. The data includes daily respiratory hospitalizations for those enrolled in the US Medicare insurance system, $PM_{2.5}$ chemical speciation concentrations from the EPA Chemical Speciation Network (CSN), and wildfire smoke data for each day from outputs of the GEOS-Chem chemical transport model. Although it is easy to replicate part of the results using most of the data, due to data confidentiality, we could not obtain the respiratory hospitalization data needed to estimate health effects. To address this, we used data from Franklin et al. (2008), which includes $PM_{2.5}$ chemical speciation data (from the EPA CSN) as well as mortality data from 25 counties in the US. This data gives daily observations from 2000 to 2005 at the county level of 18 $PM_{2.5}$ components including Aluminum (Al), Arsenic (As), Bromine (Br), Chromium (Cr), Elemental Carbon (EC), Iron (Fe), Potassium (K), Manganese (Mn), the Sodium ion (Na^+), Nickel (Ni), Nitrate (NO_3^-), the

Ammonium ion (NH_4^-), Organic Carbon (OC), Lead (Pb), Silicon (Si), Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), Vanadium (V), and Zinc (Zn). The dataset do not include wildfire smoke information, and currently available sources such as NOAA’s Hazard Mapping System (HMS) do not provide data dating back to 2000. Nevertheless, we used HMS smoke data from 2005-2023 to provide information from which we simulated smoke and non-smoke days for 2000-2005 to match the mortality data.

3.5 Simulated Data

We used a simple linear model to generate probabilities to simulate the binary variable (“smoke day” or “non-smoke day”). The coefficients were taken from a fit of a Binomial GLM on the California HMS data, where smoke was the response variable and mean $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ levels was the independent variable.

To simulate light and heavy wildfire smoke, we used data from the days that were already assigned as smoke days and considered the overall level of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ on those days. Based on the California categorical smoke data, 13.2% of smoke days had heavy smoke. Using this, we assigned smoke days with $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ levels over the 86.8th percentile as heavy smoke days, and assigned the rest of the smoke days as light smoke days.

3.6 Results

3.6.1 Propensity Score Matching

Boxplots of the log total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations on non-smoke days and smoke days in the matched dataset are shown in Figure 1. We observe a large variance in concentrations for both smoke days and non-smoke days, but the median $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations were higher on smoke days. This was expected given how we simulated the smoke days to be more likely to occur on days with higher levels of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$.

Figure 1: Boxplots for the log total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations on non-smoke days and smoke days in the matched dataset.

Figure 2 shows the predicted and observed potential log total $PM_{2.5}$ concentration outcomes, with a dot for each observed day. The ticks on the x and y axes show the observed $PM_{2.5}$ values on non-smoke days $PM_t(0)$ and smoke days $PM_t(1)$, respectively. The solid line is the 1-to-1 line $y = x$ and the dashed lines show the region $y = x \pm 0.75$, where 0.75 was the value chosen to be the variable b described in section 3.1. This variable defines when the difference between $PM_t(1)$ and $PM_t(0)$ is thought to be "small". From the plot this difference is considered to be small. The points that fall within the region bounded by the dashed line can be weighted more heavily for the principal mixture direction estimation using SIR, while the points that fall outside this region can be weighted less heavily.

Figure 2: Predicted and observed potential log total $PM_{2.5}$ concentration outcomes.

3.6.2 Sliced Inverse Regression

Figure 3 shows the SIR coefficients for each of the components being considered. This displays the principal mixture direction generated by the weighted SIR method. A positive mixture score indicates a mixture of components that more closely characterizes a smoke day, while a negative score indicates a mixture that more closely characterizes a non-smoke day. We observe that Br, Cr, Mn, and V tend to have higher concentrations on smoke days, while As, Ni, and Zn tend to have lower concentrations on those days.

3.6.3 Principal Stratification

In the estimation of the relative risk function, a natural spline with 2 degrees of freedom was used to model the relationship between the relative risk of respiratory hospitalization and the difference in predicted mixture score $x_t(1) - x_t(0)$. The 2 degrees of freedom allows for more flexibility than a linear model.

Figure 4 shows the estimated relative risk, which is a function of the difference in the predicted mixture score. The estimated relative risk decreases as the difference in predicted mixture score increases from a negative value to a positive value, indicating fewer respiratory hospitalizations

Figure 3: SIR coefficients for each of the 18 components.

as the chemical composition becomes more like that of a smoke day. The uncertainty, which is quantified by 95% confidence intervals computed using the percentile method with 5000 bootstrap replications, is also much higher for lower difference values in predicted mixture score.

The mean difference in the principal mixture score is 0.0028, which relates to an estimate of a 1.4% (95% CI: -5.2%, 7.6%) change in respiratory hospitalizations. Meanwhile, at a difference in principal mixture score of 0.008 there is an estimated 0.0% (95% CI: -7.6%, 7.3%) change in respiratory hospitalizations. At a difference in principal mixture score of -0.005, I obtain an estimate of a 2.7% (95% CI: -5.5%, 10.6%) change in respiratory hospitalizations.

3.6.4 Principal Stratification Sensitivity Analysis

The results for a sensitivity analysis are shown in Appendix A. When ρ and ω varied between 0.2 and 0.8, the main results did not change and the shape of the estimated relative risk function remained the same. However, having lower values of ρ decreased the uncertainty in the function, and therefore we set $\rho = 0$. For smaller values of b , the shape of the curve changed while retaining the downward trend from negative to positive differences in the predicted mixture score. There was also increased uncertainty for differences far from 0. However, when b was increased the main results no longer changed and the shape of the estimated relative risk function stayed the same. Also, there was more uncertainty, especially for differences in predicted mixture score far from 0, below a threshold of the value of b . This is because in those cases, there were less observations that satisfied the definition of when the difference between $PM_t(1)$ and $PM_t(0)$ is thought to be "small". Therefore, fewer observations could be used to estimate the principal mixture direction.

3.6.5 Distributed Lag

Figure 5 shows the 3-D plot of the relationships between $PM_{2.5}$ exposure, time lag, and outcome for the DLNM that includes an interaction between the smoke and total $PM_{2.5}$. In this case, the outcome is the relative risk, with compared to when the total $PM_{2.5}$ mass is at the minimum. The

Figure 4: Estimated relative risk as a function of the difference in the predicted mixture score

results are shown for time lags from 0 to 30 days. From this figure we observe that hospitalizations increase as total $PM_{2.5}$ mass increases until a lag of approximately 15 days. Beyond that the relative risk decreases, which could be an artifact of the smoke simulation or that the exposure is no longer strongly associated after 15 days. These results were mostly unaffected by the choice of spline, however having more degrees of freedom resulted in wiggly curves, likely due to overfitting.

The limitation of DLNMs and 3-D plots for visualization is that we do not have an estimate of uncertainty. To obtain an uncertainty estimate (i.e. confidence interval), the effect estimates would need to be generated for particular lags. Figure 6 shows these plots for lags 0, 5, 15, and 28, and $PM_{2.5}$ levels at the 0.1st, 5th, 95th and 99.5th percentiles for the DLNM with the interaction term. From these plots we observe that the effect estimates are significant at larger $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations and for lags between 7-22 days. The uncertainty is large both short lags (0-5 days) and longer lags (23-30 days).

The overall effect, which is the sum of the effects over all time lags versus the relative risk in terms of total $PM_{2.5}$ mass is shown in Figure 7. We observe more clearly that in the DLNM the overall effect and uncertainty grows larger as total $PM_{2.5}$ levels increase compared to the DLNM with stratification by smoke and non-smoke days.

The overall effect estimates at the 0.1st, 5th, 95th, and 99.5th percentiles are shown the table below. Since the interaction term is a product with the binary smoke variable, the 0.1st and 5th percentiles are both 0 because there are enough non smoke days for that to occur.

Percentile	DLNM with interaction term	
	Total Mass	Overall Effect Estimate (95% CI)
0.1	0	1.00 (1.00, 1.00)
5	0	1.00 (1.00, 1.00)
95	25.6	1.53 (1.25, 1.89)
99.5	76.7	3.61 (1.93, 6.73)

Figure 5: 3-D plots for the DLNM with the interaction term between the smoke variable and total $PM_{2.5}$ level variable.

4 Discussion

The principal stratification method is useful because it allows for easier interpretation of the different effects of pollutant mixtures by creating a principal mixture scores on smoke and non-smoke days. In this way, the effect of the air pollution mixture on health outcomes can be interpreted with these scores instead of having an effect for every single component being considered. When the number of pollutants in the mixture is high, the interpretations of scores is more straightforward.

The propensity score matching step in this analysis was useful because it not only avoids confounding with time, space, and temperature variables, but could also provide robustness against model misspecification (Ho et al. (2007)).

Compared to Peng et al. (2022), we found similar results for the propensity score matching and the principal stratification. However, since the smoke data in our application were simulated, we did not expect obtain similar results for the sliced inverse regression. Our SIR results should be interpreted with caution, and the coefficients that were obtained were quite different than Peng et al. for many of the components. For example, we found much larger positive coefficients for Br and a negative coefficient for As that is smaller in magnitude. Peng et al. (2022) found that the chemical composition of smoke days could be less harmful than the chemical composition of non-smoke days, suggesting that the chemical composition of wildfire smoke $PM_{2.5}$ could be less toxic than particulate matter pollution from other sources. It is important to remember that this method controls for other variables such as $PM_{2.5}$ concentration. In reality, smoke days can have much larger $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations (as shown in Figure 1), which could lead to more adverse health effects than non-smoke days.

When incorporating the DLNM to the principal stratification method, one challenge is that there are numerous parameters in the model to choose, such as basis type and maximum lag. To deal

Figure 6: Relative risk with confidence intervals for lags 0, 5, 15, and 28, and $PM_{2.5}$ levels at the 0.1st, 5th, 95th and 99.5th percentiles for the DLNM with the interaction term

with this, it may be useful to conduct more sensitivity analyses and to use regression diagnostics to ensure that the choices made lead to a good model for the data.

Some interesting extensions to the DLM method have been proposed. For example, spatio-temporal DLMs could be useful to incorporate both time lags and spatial contrasts into the model (Rotejanaprasert et al. (2021)). Development has also been made for DLMs with variable selection (Antonelli et al. (2022)). In addition, while the proposed DLNM is completely parametric, some non-parametric methods have been proposed. For example, to describe the distributed lag curve and deal with non-linear effects, some approaches based on penalized regression with low-rank smoothers have been proposed (Zanobetti (2000); Muggeo (2008); Schimek (2009)).

In addition to incorporating the time lag into the model, another extension could be to examine the change in $PM_{2.5}$ levels in different regions of the US, since the pollution mixture from wildfires in different eco-regions can change. While this was considered in setting up the propensity score matching, it may be useful to repeat this analysis on more locations while stratifying by eco-region.

Another extension could be to use a continuous measure for the proportion of $PM_{2.5}$ associated with wildfire smoke, instead of a binary or categorical smoke variable. This would allow higher dimensions for the SIR method, which would address the issue of having possible days where score values are similar but $PM_{2.5}$ mixtures are different (Peng et al. (2022)). Another issue with the SIR method is that it ignores higher order information, which could better capture changes in $PM_{2.5}$ mixtures due to wildfires (Peng et al. (2022)). Instead, the covariance structure of the data could be used to capture these changes with approaches such as principal Hessian directions or sliced average variance estimation (Peng et al. (2022)).

A limitation with wildfire data is that the number of smoke days can be small. The simulated smoke data reflects this fact as well. Because of this, it is difficult to obtain reliable estimates, especially for methods that involve stratification between smoke days and non-smoke days. Finally,

Figure 7: Plots of overall effect for the DLNM with stratification and the DLNM with the interaction term between the smoke variable and total $PM_{2.5}$ level variable.

another general limitation is that the smoke data in our analysis are simulated, so it is difficult to evaluate the final results. Nevertheless, the approach is demonstrated along with the extension of the distributed lag. Our future goal is replicate our approach with a complete dataset of wildfire smoke, chemical speciation, and health outcome data.

Appendix

A Sensitivity Analysis

Figure 8: Estimated relative risk as a function of the difference in the predicted mixture score for $\rho = 0.2, \omega = 0.2, b = 0.75$.

Figure 9: Estimated relative risk as a function of the difference in the predicted mixture score for $\rho = 0.8, \omega = 0.2, b = 0.75$.

Figure 10: Estimated relative risk as a function of the difference in the predicted mixture score for $\rho = 0.5, \omega = 0.8, b = 0.75$.

Figure 11: Estimated relative risk as a function of the difference in the predicted mixture score for $\rho = 0.5, \omega = 0.2, b = 0.4$.

Figure 12: Estimated relative risk as a function of the difference in the predicted mixture score for $\rho = 0.5, \omega = 0.2, b = 1.5$.

References

- Aguilera, R., Corringham, T., Gershunov, A., and Benmarhnia, T. (2021). Wildfire smoke impacts respiratory health more than fine particles from other sources: Observational evidence from southern california. *Nature Communications*, 12(1).
- Antonelli, J., Wilson, A., and Coull, B. A. (2022). Multiple exposure distributed lag models with variable selection. *Biostatistics*.
- Boaggio, K., LeDuc, S. D., Rice, R. B., Duffney, P. F., Foley, K. M., Holder, A. L., McDow, S., and Weaver, C. P. (2022). Beyond Particulate Matter Mass: Heightened Levels of Lead and Other Pollutants Associated with Destructive Fire Events in California. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 56(20):14272–14283.
- Dominici, F., Peng, R. D., Barr, C. D., and Bell, M. L. (2010). Protecting human health from air pollution. *Epidemiology*, 21(2):187–194.
- Franklin, M., Koutrakis, P., and Schwartz, J. (2008). The role of particle composition on the association between pm2.5 and mortality. *Epidemiology*, 19(5):680–689.
- Gasparrini, A. (2011). Distributed lag linear and non-linear models in R: the package dlnm. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 43(8):1–20.
- Gasparrini, A., Armstrong, B., and Kenward, M. G. (2010). Distributed lag non-linear models. *Statistics in Medicine*, 29(21):2224–2234.

- Ho, D. E., Imai, K., King, G., and Stuart, E. A. (2007). Matching as nonparametric preprocessing for reducing model dependence in parametric causal inference. *Political Analysis*, 15(3):199–236.
- Liu, J. C. and Peng, R. D. (2018). The impact of wildfire smoke on compositions of fine particulate matter by ecoregion in the western us. *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology*, 29(6):765–776.
- Muggeo, V. M. (2008). Modeling temperature effects on mortality: Multiple segmented relationships with common break points. *Biostatistics*, 9(4):613–620.
- Peng, R. D., Liu, J. C., McCormack, M. C., Mickley, L. J., and Bell, M. L. (2022). Estimating the health effects of environmental mixtures using principal stratification. *Statistics in Medicine*, 41(10):1815–1828.
- Rotejanaprasert, C., Ekapirat, N., Sudathip, P., and Maude, R. J. (2021). Bayesian spatio-temporal distributed lag modeling for delayed climatic effects on sparse malaria incidence data. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 21(1).
- Schimek, M. G. (2009). Semiparametric penalized generalized additive models for environmental research and epidemiology. *Environmetrics*, 20(6):699–717.
- Schwartz, J. (2000). The distributed lag between air pollution and daily deaths. *Epidemiology*, 11(3):320–326.
- Zanobetti, A. (2000). Generalized additive distributed lag models: Quantifying mortality displacement. *Biostatistics*, 1(3):279–292.